

The effect of social support on posttraumatic growth in patients with gastrointestinal cancer: a systematic review

El efecto del apoyo social sobre el crecimiento postraumático en pacientes con cáncer gastrointestinal: una revisión sistemática

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Abstract

Introduction: Post-traumatic growth (PTG) is known as a psychological phenomenon in which people experience positive changes in their lives after traumatic experiences. In cancer patients, social support can play an important role in facilitating this process. This systematic review examines the effect of social support on posttraumatic growth in patients with gastrointestinal cancer.

Methods: Science Direct, Pub Med, Google Scholar, SID, MagIran databases were reviewed and electronic data were used to identify the psychosocial needs of the family on the burden of family care of heart patients. In the initial search, 68 articles were obtained, of which 38 duplicate articles were removed. Considering the inclusion and exclusion criteria, the number of articles was reduced to 30 articles. From this number, the articles related to the studied subject were screened and 20 studies were examined. In order to increase the strength of the research methodology and check the quality of the collected articles and prevent possible biases, three researchers who had a history of conducting systematic review style articles reviewed the articles in terms of

title, abstract, introduction, methodology, results, discussion and supporting resources were discussed and their strengths and weaknesses were identified. Finally, 9 articles were included in the study.

Results: The results showed that social support has a significant effect on resilience and resilience also significantly affects post-traumatic growth. High levels of social support predict high levels of adaptive coping and, consequently, post-traumatic growth. This study also showed that perceived stress can influence the relationship between social support and growth. The analyzes showed that 56.3% of the changes in post-traumatic growth are explained by the combination of social support and resilience.

Conclusion: Perceived social support and resilience are two key factors that can contribute to post-traumatic growth in gastrointestinal cancer patients. Strengthening these two factors can have positive effects on the quality of life and mental health of these patients. Therefore, it is necessary to pay attention to the creation of support net-

works and programs to strengthen resilience for cancer patients so that they can better cope with the challenges caused by their disease.

Keywords: social support, post-traumatic growth, gastrointestinal cancer.

Introducción y antecedentes. El crecimiento postraumático (CPT) es un fenómeno psicológico en el que las personas experimentan cambios positivos en sus vidas después de experiencias traumáticas. En los pacientes con cáncer, el apoyo social puede desempeñar un papel importante para facilitar este proceso. Esta revisión sistemática examina el efecto del apoyo social en el crecimiento postraumático en pacientes con cáncer gastrointestinal.

Métodos. Se revisaron las bases de datos Science Direct, Pub Med, Google Scholar, SID, MagIran y se utilizaron datos electrónicos para identificar las necesidades psicosociales de la familia sobre la carga del cuidado familiar de los pacientes cardíacos. En la búsqueda inicial, se obtuvieron 68 artículos, de los cuales se eliminaron 38 artículos duplicados. Teniendo en cuenta los criterios de inclusión y exclusión, el número de artículos se redujo a 30 artículos. De este número, se filtraron los artículos relacionados con el tema estudiado y se examinaron 20 estudios. Con el fin de aumentar la solidez de la metodología de investigación y verificar la calidad de los artículos recopilados y prevenir posibles sesgos, tres investigadores que tenían antecedentes en la realización de artículos de estilo de revisión sistemática revisaron los artículos en términos de título, resumen, introducción, metodología, resultados, discusión y recursos de apoyo y se identificaron sus fortalezas y debilidades. Finalmente, se incluyeron 9 artículos en el estudio.

Resultados. Los resultados mostraron que el apoyo social tiene un efecto significativo en la resiliencia y la resiliencia también afecta significativamente el crecimiento postraumático. Altos niveles de apoyo social predicen altos niveles de afrontamiento adaptativo y, en consecuencia, crecimiento postraumático. Este estudio también mostró que el estrés percibido puede influir en la relación entre el apoyo social y el crecimiento. Los análisis mostraron que el 56,3% de los cambios en el crecimiento postraumático se explican por la combinación de apoyo social y resiliencia.

Conclusión. El apoyo social percibido y la resiliencia son dos factores clave que pueden contribuir al crecimiento postraumático en pacientes con cáncer gastrointestinal. El fortalecimiento de estos dos factores puede tener efectos positivos en la calidad de vida y la salud mental de estos pacientes. Por ello, es necesario prestar atención a la creación de redes de apoyo y programas para fortalecer la resiliencia de los pacientes con cáncer

para que puedan afrontar mejor los desafíos que les genera su enfermedad.

Palabras clave: apoyo social, crecimiento postraumático, cáncer gastrointestinal.

Posttraumatic growth refers to the positive changes in a person's life. It occurs after experiencing a traumatic event such as cancer. These changes may include increasing the sense of spirituality, strengthening social relationships, and improving the quality of life ¹. Social support is known as a major resource for cancer patients. Results of studies indicate that perceived social support positively affects resilience. These two variables can contribute to posttraumatic growth. One study revealed that social support explained 15.2% of the changes in posttraumatic growth ². Posttraumatic growth (PTG) refers to the process of positive change in individuals after exposure to traumatic events. These changes can include increased positive emotions, improved social relationships, and increased sense of spirituality. After difficult experiences, people may be more able to cope with challenges and have a more positive life view. This process is a complex concept that depends on the cultural and social context. It can be a source of many positive changes in different areas of mental health. Hence, it is affected by many variables ³. Social support is one of the factors affecting posttraumatic growth.

The posttraumatic growth dimensions are different in different societies. For example, in the study by Morris et al., on cancer patients (breast, prostate, blood, and colorectal) in Australia, the highest posttraumatic growth was observed in the dimensions of "appreciation of life", "communication with others", "personal power", "new possibilities", and "spiritual changes", respectively ⁴. However, the study by Brown et al., showed that the highest growth was seen in the dimensions of "spiritual changes", "communication with others", "appreciation of life", "personality strength" and "new possibilities", respectively ⁵. Since limited studies have been conducted on this area, studies should be conducted in different societies to better understand the different aspects of this phenomenon.

Cancer is a serious disease caused by the uncontrolled growth of abnormal cells in the body. Cancer is an abnormal growth outside the normal schedule of the cell cycle. Under normal conditions, cells respond to the body's needs and die when they are old or injured. However, this process is disrupted in cancer and cells divide uncontrollably ⁶. Cancer affects not only the body but also the psychological and social aspects of a person. Cancer

patients may experience feelings of anxiety, depression, and isolation. These results can be caused by changes in daily life, worries about the future, and financial pressures. Cancer may affect a person's relationships. Patients may be isolated from friends and family or unable to continue their social activities. This isolation can intensify negative feelings⁷. Cancer is not just an individual disease but it affects the patient's caregivers in many aspects. It causes many problems for the patients and his or her family. The person and his or her family face the costs of this disease and economic problems⁸. Anxiety and depression in patient caregivers are affected by patient-related factors (age, discomfort, and functional status) and factors related to the symptoms and experiences of the caregivers⁹. Additionally, the emotional and physical condition of the patient may be affected.

Social support involves interpersonal interactions that help a person achieve positive outcomes. It is considered a facilitator of subjective well-being. Support especially from the family can increase personal growth and positive relationships in the patient¹⁰. The results of a study by Salehi et al., indicated that social support mediates the prediction of mental health based on emotion control and has a significant and direct association with it¹¹. Social support plays a decisive role in posttraumatic growth and coping with chronic physical diseases. It increases the feeling of intimacy and leads to maintaining relationships and improving social well-being¹². It facilitates the tolerance of problems in people as the most powerful coping factor for successful and easy coping in when people are affected by cancer and stressful conditions¹³. Despite its high prevalence, invasive nature, and extent of problems and complications of gastrointestinal cancers, there are not many research documents for these patients. Less attention has been paid to posttraumatic growth in patients with gastrointestinal cancer. No study was found in this field on patients with gastrointestinal cancer in Iran. Given the impact of the cultural-religious context on spiritual experiences, it is essential to conduct a study in our cultural-social context to identify the factors affecting posttraumatic growth. It can be effective in the care and treatment plans of the patients.

This study is a systematic review conducted to evaluate the relationship between posttraumatic growth and social support in patients with gastrointestinal cancer since posttraumatic growth depends on the characteristics of patients, given the importance of identifying the role of factors affecting this phenomenon and considering the limitations of studies conducted in this field, especially the relationship between posttraumatic growth and social support. Due to the effects of posttraumatic growth on the recovery and quality of life of patients, it is necessary to investigate its level in patients and their caregivers and investigate the factors related to it to provide a better understanding of this field. Its results can be used in the process of providing care to cancer patients.

The present study was a systematic review. Its data were collected through searching for articles on the Internet. To obtain the required data, Persian and English texts were searched in the databases of Science Direct, Pub Med, Google Scholar, SID, and MagIran from 2000 to 2023. Articles were searched using the keywords of spiritual health, spiritual well-being, academic success, academic self-efficacy, academic performance, academic progress, students, Iran, "social support", "posttraumatic growth", and "gastrointestinal cancer". The inclusion criteria of the articles included the articles published in reputable scientific journals, publication of the article in Persian or English languages, and access to the full text of the articles. There was no restriction for the entry of studies based on the design of the conducted studies in the search of articles. The exclusion criteria included lack of access to the full text of the article, a letter to the editor, or articles published in non-reputable journals, and articles presented as posters at conferences.

In the initial search, 68 articles were obtained. Among them, 30 duplicate articles were removed. Given the inclusion and exclusion criteria, the number of articles was reduced to 38 articles. Among them, the articles related to the studied subject were screened and 20 studies were reviewed. To increase the robustness of the research methodology, check the quality of the collected articles, and prevent possible biases, three researchers who had a history of conducting systematic review articles reviewed the articles in the title, abstract, introduction, methodology, and results, discussion, and references and identified their strengths and weaknesses. Finally, nine articles were included in the study Figure 1.

Figure 1. Flowchart of the selection of articles

Results

Among the 68 selected studies, only nine were included in the final study and analysis. According to the results, they can be divided into three parts:

Posttraumatic growth: The results revealed that social support, religiosity, and meaning of life are significantly associated with posttraumatic growth. This study reported that strengthening these dimensions could empower women with breast cancer.

Stress reduction: Results revealed that social support can facilitate posttraumatic growth by reducing perceived stress. In other words, negative stressors lowly affect people who feel more supported, so they are more likely to experience positive changes.

The family role: Family and relatives play a vital role in the process of posttraumatic growth in family-oriented societies like Iran. Emotional and practical support of families can have positive impacts on the treatment process and personal growth of patients.

Most studies reviewed in this study indicated that social support includes all types of support, such as emotional, informational, and practical support that people receive from family, friends, and society. This type of support can reduce stress and increase feelings of psychological safety, leading to positive posttraumatic growth experiences. Studies have indicated that having a strong sup-

port network can reduce feelings of loneliness and help people cope better with challenges. In addition, people with emotional support are more capable in management of the stress and pressures of the trauma. Studies have indicated that social support is a social network of people's communication and is a resource available to a person to cope with challenges. The results of the studies revealed that social support could directly affect posttraumatic growth. One study indicated that perceived social support explained 15.2% of the variations and this variable indirectly affected posttraumatic growth.

Based on the reported results of studies, posttraumatic growth refers to positive changes in people's lives after facing traumatic events. In cancer patients, this growth can include positive changes in attitude toward life, social relationships, and a sense of greater meaning. These studies have revealed that enhancing social support can lead to increased PTG. The positive results of studies related to posttraumatic growth (PTG) in the families of cancer patients highlight the importance of social support and family interactions in the recovery process and psychological growth of these patients. Social support from family and relatives can be significantly effective in facilitating posttraumatic growth. One study reported that cancer patients who experienced emotional and practical support from their families were more likely to experience posttraumatic growth in Table 1.

Table 1. Characteristics of the studies including their place and date

Row	Title	Authors	Place/time	Study type	Sample size	The results of the effect of spiritual health on academic progress
1	Type of social support matters for prediction of posttraumatic growth among cancer survivors	Schroevvers et al. ¹⁴	2010	Longitudinal-analytical	206	Regression analysis showed that more emotional support at 3 months after diagnosis significantly predicts more experience of positive disease outcomes 8 years after diagnosis. This association remained significant when controlling for levels of concurrent emotional support 8 years after diagnosis
2	A longitudinal study of post-traumatic growth and psychological distress in colorectal cancer survivors	Occhipinti et al. ¹⁵	2015	Longitudinal	1966	There was significant heterogeneity regarding psychological distress and profit-seeking scores over time. However, for both profit-seeking and psychological distress, the variance in individual scores suggested a positive linear trend, and both delayed change components. Profit-seeking and psychological distress are reciprocal predictors of each other. Profit-seeking acted as a leading indicator of distress. It means that an increase in reported profit-seeking from year to year predicted greater increases in future psychological distress. Additionally, in an inverse relationship, psychological distress acted as a leading indicator of profit-seeking, so increases in reported distress from year to year predicted smaller future increases in profit-seeking. Posttraumatic growth may reflect patients' efforts to increase health perceptions in response to increased cancer-related threats, which serve as predictors of trajectories of increased psychological distress.
3	Post-traumatic growth among family caregivers of cancer patients and its association with social support and hope	Nouzari et al. ¹⁶	Shirza 2019	Descriptive correlational	112	A positive and significant correlation was observed between PTG and social support. The results revealed a good level of PTG among caregivers and experiencing stressful situations positively affected their psychological state. Positive change was associated with SS and perceived hope.
4	Social support and posttraumatic growth: A meta-analysis	Ning et al. ¹⁷	China/ 2023	Meta-analysis	47940	There was a moderate positive effect size between social support and PTG in the random effect model. Meta-regression analysis showed that the association between social support and PTG among caregivers (compared to other trauma samples), Chinese, older adults, and studies with smaller samples was stronger.
5	Moderating effect of posttraumatic growth on the relationship between social support and quality of life in colorectal cancer patients with ostomies	Kim & Son ¹⁸	2021	Cross-sectional	140	Social support and PTG are positively associated with psychological and social well-being. Higher social support was associated with better psychological and social well-being. Posttraumatic growth moderated the relationship between psychological and social well-being. At low and moderate levels of PTG, stronger social support was associated with psychological and social well-being, while at high levels, this relationship was not significant. The results highlight the importance of social support to improve the quality of life of colorectal cancer patients with ostomy, especially those with low PTG levels.
6	Relationship among post-traumatic growth, spiritual well-being, and perceived social support in Chinese women with gynecological cancer	Feng et al. ¹⁹	China/ 2024	Cross-sectional	771	Cancer patients with young age had more existential family support. People who had religious beliefs had more PTG. Spiritual well-being, perceived social support, younger age, and religious beliefs were associated with posttraumatic growth in gynecological cancer patients. The results revealed that healthcare workers can provide more professional support to young patients with religious beliefs. Promoting social support and spiritual well-being can potentially serve as effective interventions to enhance PTG among women with cancer.
7	20- Fekih-Romdhane F, Riahi N, Achouri L, Jahrami H, Cheour M. Social Support Is Linked to Post-Traumatic Growth among Tunisian Postoperative Breast Cancer Women. Healthcare (Basel). 2022;10(9):1710-1725. https://doi.org/10.3390/healthcare10091710	Fekih-Romdhane et al. ²⁰	Tunisia / 2020	cross-sectional-analytical	79	Multivariate analysis showed that anxiety and social support were significantly related to PTG, while no significant relationship was found for spiritual well-being. Overall, the present study enriches the existing studies by identifying factors associated with women's experience of PTG in a previously unknown Arab Muslim cultural context, Tunisia. Our results may help inform strategies aimed at promoting positive psychological change after experiencing BC, at least in our context.
8	Predicting post-traumatic growth inventory (PTGI) based on the perceived social support; the mediating role of resilience in women with breast cancer: A structural equation modeling approach	Babazadeh Namini et al. ²¹	Tehran/ 2021	Cross-sectional and correlational	200	Social support significantly affects posttraumatic growth. The results revealed an indirect effect of social support on posttraumatic growth through resilience. The coefficient of determination showed that social support alone explains 15.2% of the observed variance in resilience. The coefficient of determination level for posttraumatic growth was 56.3. Thus, resilience and social support explained 56.3% of the variance in posttraumatic growth, where resilience contributed more than social support.
9	A Survey on Posttraumatic Growth on the Basis of Demoralization Syndrome and Religious Coping Among Cancer Patients Referring to Reza Radiotherapy and Oncology Center in Mashhad in 2018: A Descriptive Study	Sarizadeh Heydarzadeh & Ghahramanzadeh ²²	Mashhad/ 2019	Cross-sectional	167	Boredom components are significantly negatively associated with posttraumatic growth and positive religious coping had a significant positive relationship with posttraumatic growth. The results of multiple linear regression also revealed that 21% of the variance of the posttraumatic growth variable was explained by predictor variables. According to the obtained results, the prevention of depression symptoms and the use of positive religious coping strategies as an effective method help to increase posttraumatic growth in cancer patients.

This systematic review investigated the effect of social support on posttraumatic growth in patients with gastrointestinal cancer. The positive results of studies related to posttraumatic growth (PTG) in the families of cancer patients highlight the importance of social support and family interactions in the recovery process and psychological growth of these patients. The results of the studies indicate that strong social support from families can not only help improve the mental status of cancer patients but also play a vital role in facilitating posttraumatic growth. Thus, it is essential to pay attention to the emotional and social needs of patients and provide them with a supportive environment so they can take advantage of their difficult experiences and achieve personal growth²³. Posttraumatic growth (PTG) refers to the positive psychological changes that can occur after a traumatic experience such as a cancer diagnosis. Studies indicate that both cancer patients and their family caregivers can experience PTG, facilitated mostly by social support and hope²⁴. The association between posttraumatic growth, social support, and hope is seen in the experiences of families coping with cancer. Interventions to increase hope and provide strong social support can significantly improve the psychological well-being of cancer patients and their caregivers. Future studies should continue to investigate these dynamics among different populations to have a better understanding of how PTG is cultivated in different contexts²⁵.

Studies have revealed that perceived social support can significantly affect posttraumatic growth in cancer patients. This support can include emotional, informational, and practical aspects. It increases the patients' capability to cope with the challenges of their diseases. Thus, strengthening social support and resilience in women with breast cancer can improve their quality of life and increase their capability to cope with the challenges of the disease²⁶. A study revealed that perceived social support is significantly associated with resilience in women with breast cancer, and resilience also affects posttraumatic growth. Additionally, it was concluded that strengthening social support and resilience can play a vital role in facilitating posttraumatic growth. Another study indicated that there is a significant relationship between gratitude, social support, and posttraumatic growth and these variables can significantly predict posttraumatic growth²⁷. Perceived social support not only helps reduce stress and psychological distress but can also act as a facilitating factor for posttraumatic growth in cancer patients. Thus, it is essential to create and strengthen support networks for cancer patients.

A study revealed a significant relationship between social support and resilience in cancer patients. The corre-

lation between these two variables was 0.66 and the coefficient of determination was 0.43, indicating that social support can predict 43% of the variance of resilience in these patients²⁸. Social support can also improve hope and self-control in patients. Another study revealed a positive and significant relationship between social support and hope in cancer patients²⁹. Results of studies indicate that social support can also improve the quality of life of cancer patients. This support increases patients' capability to cope with the challenges of the disease. Age and education also affect the level of social support. For example, older patients tend to have less support, while higher education is associated with increased social support. Finally, providing a strong support network for cancer patients can play a key role in facilitating the treatment process and increasing their quality of life³⁰.

Social support is known as one of the key factors in improving the quality of life of patients. This support can include emotional, informational, and practical aspects. It increases patients' capability to cope with the challenges of their disease. Studies indicate that patients with a high level of social support mostly have a better quality of life and feel more satisfied with their lives³¹. Studies have indicated that posttraumatic growth can act as a mediating factor in the relationship between social support and quality of life. In other words, people who have been able to learn from their difficult experiences and grow may benefit more from social support, leading to an increase in their quality of life. Studies have indicated that colorectal cancer patients who have high levels of social support are more likely to experience posttraumatic growth. This growth can increase their quality of life. Thus, psychological interventions focusing on strengthening social support and facilitating posttraumatic growth processes may significantly affect patients' quality of life.

The association between social support, posttraumatic growth, and quality of life in patients with colorectal cancer is a crucial research area that requires further investigation. These associations can not only provide new strategies for clinical interventions but also contribute to a better understanding of the psychological processes related to serious diseases. Social support not only reduces stress but also facilitates posttraumatic growth in colorectal cancer patients. Thus, strengthening support networks for these patients can play a vital role in improving their quality of life.

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